

An Algorithm Comparison for Dynamic Optimization Problems

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Abstract

This work presents a study on the performance of several algorithms on different continuous Dynamic Optimization Problems. Eight algorithms have been used: SORIGA (an evolutionary algorithm), an agents-based algorithm, the mQSO (a widely used multi-population PSO) as well as three heuristic-rule-based variations of it, and two trajectory-based cooperative strategies. The algorithms have been tested on the Moving Peaks Benchmark and the dynamic version of the Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions. For each problem, a wide variety of configuration variations have been used, emphasizing the influence of dynamism, and using a full-factorial experimental design. The results give an interesting overview of the properties of the algorithms and their applicability, and provide useful hints to face new problems of this type with the best algorithmic approach. Additionally, a recently introduced methodology for comparing a high number of experimental results in a graphical way is used.

Keywords: dynamic optimization problems, evolutionary algorithms, PSO, multi-agents, cooperative strategies, MPB, ackley, griewank, rastrigin

1. Introduction

Dynamic Optimization Problems (DOPs) have been gaining a growing interest from the research community in the past decade due to its closeness to real-world

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situations (trade market prediction, meteorological forecast, robotics motion control, etc [1–3]). These types of optimization problems differ from the traditional, static ones in the presence of time-dependent properties that may affect the fitness function, constraints, number of variables or their domain, etc. The interested reader is referred to [4] for an extensive review of DOP literature.

In order to test the different algorithmic approaches to these problems, several benchmarks have been proposed in the literature. Among the most used ones are the Moving Peaks Benchmark, MPB [1], as well as the dynamic versions of several difficult functions traditionally used in static optimization, like, e.g., Ackley, Griewank, Rastrigin, Rosenbrock, Schwefel, etc (see, for example, the test benchmark used in the dynamic optimization competition of the 2009 IEEE-CEC conference [5]).

A high number of methods that deal with DOPs has already been proposed, but there are not yet clear criteria about which one is better to apply in each situation or how to face a new problem instance. Moreover, an algorithm may be well-suited for some problem configurations, but behave worse in others. Instead of developing an always best-performing method (remember the *no-free-lunch* theorem [6]), it may be more interesting to know which are the favorable conditions for each algorithm in order to choose the best option. In this work, we introduce a first approach to this question, where we have selected a set of algorithms to compare their performance in different test benchmarks. However, we have focused mainly on establishing a robust comparison methodology, rather than on selecting the most state-of-the-art algorithms in the literature. Therefore, we have chosen mostly proposals of ourselves, because of their source-code availability and ease of adaptation to the problems, although, in general, we have attempted to select methods that are representative of diverse algorithmic families.

Traditionally, the most commonly used algorithms in DOPs have been Genetic Algorithms (GA) and Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) [1, 2, 7–9]. An special remark is deserved to the Random Immigrants Genetic Algorithm (RIGA) [10], a GA algorithm aimed at maintaining a high level of diversity, which is a key aspect in DOPs. However, other approaches have been more recently applied to these problems, outperforming GAs and EAs in some cases.

Particle Swarm Optimization, PSO, [11] is a quite competitive one, with several DOP-oriented proposals [12–15]. Particularly, a PSO variant with multi-swarms, and quantum and trajectory particles, the mQSO, [3] has obtained good results and is frequently mentioned in the literature [16–18]. Some of our recent proposals include adding heuristic rules to this mQSO [19], improving its performance.

We have also conducted some experiments studying how cooperation between multiple optimization subcomponents may be applied to DOPs, concluding that this approach is also highly competitive. These proposals include cooperative multi-agent systems [20, 21], or more recently, a centralized scheme where a coordinator manages the information exchanged among a group of trajectory-based metaheuristic solvers (i.e., Tabu-Search solvers) [22, 23].

Given these antecedents, the objective of this paper is to compare a variety of different algorithmic families for DOP's, using some of the previously mentioned proposals, in order to gain knowledge on their generic properties, behavior and performance, as well as setting the bases for future comparison studies. The chosen algorithms are:

- an Evolutionary Algorithm, SORIGA [8], based in the RIGA approach,
- the standard mQSO [3] as well as 3 of its variations based on heuristic rules [19], that are named after the rule they use (*Change Rule*, *Rand Rule*, and *Both Rule*),
- the cooperative multi-agent algorithm proposed in [21],
- and finally, two trajectory-based cooperative strategies with different cooperation schemes, *independent* and *reactive* [23].

The test-case scenarios were chosen to include different representative benchmarks, namely the MPB and the dynamic versions of the Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions. For each problem, a wide range of configurations which emphasize the influence of dynamism have been tested (variations of *change period*, *severity* and *dimensionality*), with a full-factorial experimental design combining all of them.

Additionally, due to the high number of problem configurations tested for each algorithm, a recent technique for comparing the results is used. This technique, SRCS, is based on the combination of statistical tests for creating a ranking of the algorithms, using color schemes to present the results in a graphical way, more condensed and expressive than numerical tables.

The paper is structured as follows: each of the algorithms is briefly introduced in Sect. 2, giving a general overview of their behavior. The MPB and the dynamic versions of the Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions are described in Sect. 3. The different variations of the problems' configurations, the performance measure, and the SRCS technique used for presenting the results are explained in

Sect. 4. The experimental results and their analysis is provided in Sect. 5, while Sect. 6 gives the conclusions obtained from the experiments.

2. Algorithms

2.1. SORIGA

SORIGA (Self Organized Random Immigrants Genetic Algorithm) was proposed by Tinós and Yang in [8]. It is a variation of RIGA (Random Immigrants Genetic Algorithm) [10], a genetic algorithm where the flux of immigrants increases the diversity of the population.

The main modification introduced by SORIGA is the use of two different populations: the main population and a sub-population. Assignment of individuals to each population is performed dynamically during the execution of the algorithm, and crossover is only allowed between individuals within the same population. The pseudocode of SORIGA is given in Algorithms 1 and 2.

At the beginning, all the individuals belong to the main population, but as evolution goes on, individuals are extracted from it and assigned to the sub-population. This is done by means of the *replaceFractionPopulation()* function (Algorithm 1, line 8, and Algorithm 2). This function selects the individual with the lowest fitness and other $r_r - 1$ more around it (r_r is a user-defined parameter, the replacement rate), assign them to the sub-population, and replace them with random individuals. In case the less-fitted individual already belongs to the sub-population, all individuals are extracted from the sub-population and put back to the main population. Then, traditional mutation and crossover operators are applied, with the previously mentioned modification, i.e., that crossover is only allowed among individuals within the same population. Tinós and Yang show in their paper that the process of individuals joining the sub-population when the main population is close to a local optimum is similar to a “chain reaction”, thus increasing the diversity (this feature being called *self-organized criticality*, SOC[24]).

Originally, SORIGA was tested in a *discrete* DOP. In order to adapt it to *continuous* DOP’s, we have re-implemented it using continuous crossover and mutation operators. For the crossover operator, the well-known BLX- α operator [25] was chosen. Regarding the mutation operator, a simple one in the real domain was implemented, which randomizes one component of an individual in the whole search space domain.

The parameter settings used in the experimentation for the SORIGA algorithm are summarized in Table 1. In general, the parameter values were chosen to be the

Algorithm 1: SORIGA

```
1  $P \leftarrow$  population ;
2  $r_c \leftarrow$  crossover rate ;
3  $r_m \leftarrow$  mutation rate ;
4  $r_r \leftarrow$  replacement rate ;
5 initializePopulation( $P$ );
6 evaluatePopulation( $P$ );
7 while stopping condition is not met do
8    $P_{new} \leftarrow$  replaceFractionPopulation( $P, r_r$ );
9    $P_{new} \leftarrow P_{new} +$  crossover( $P, r_c$ );
10   $P_{new} \leftarrow$  mutation( $P_{new}, r_m$ );
11  evaluatePopulation( $P_{new}$ );
12   $P \leftarrow P_{new}$ ;
13 end
```

ones used in Tinós and Yang paper, with the exception of the BLX- α settings (not available in the original proposal since it was tested on a discrete problem) and the population size (in the original paper it was set to 120, a value that showed poor performance in some preliminary test in these problems).

2.2. The Agents algorithm

The Agents algorithm is a decentralized cooperative strategy that was originally described on [20, 21]. The full description of the general design of this method can be found in the previous references and here we will only present a brief summary of its main characteristics. Its pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 3.

The algorithm consists in a set of agents that traverse a fixed-size matrix, or *grid*, of solutions, trying to improve each solution they arrive to in each step. The way in which these solutions are improved depend on the neighbors of the cell in the grid, and the structure of the grid determines the topology of the *neighborhoods* (in this case, a Moore neighborhood topology is used, where a solution in the cell (i, j) is neighbor of $(i - 1, j - 1)$, $(i - 1, j)$, $(i - 1, j + 1)$, $(i, j - 1)$, $(i, j + 1)$, $(i + 1, j - 1)$, $(i + 1, j)$ and $(i + 1, j + 1)$). Please note that with this definition, close solutions in terms of grid neighborhoods do not necessarily imply closeness in terms of solution-space distances.

The algorithm is run until the stop condition is met (usually, after some number of fitness function evaluations or changes in the environment). In each iteration,

Algorithm 2: SORIGA, replaceFractionPopulation(P, r_r)

```
1  $P_{new} \leftarrow$  empty population;
2  $i \leftarrow$  index of the individual of  $P$  with the lowest fitness;
3 if  $P[i].replaced = false$  then
    // reset subpopulation to contain no individual
4   for each individual  $j$  in  $P$  do
5      $P[j].replaced \leftarrow false$ ;
6   end
7 end
8 for each individual  $j$  in  $P$  do
    // if individual  $j$  is one of the  $r_r$  individuals
    // around individual  $i$ , randomize it and add it
    // to the subpopulation; otherwise, just copy
    // it
9   if  $i - \lceil (r_r - 1)/2 \rceil \leq j \leq i + \lfloor (r_r - 1)/2 \rfloor$  then
10     $P_{new}[j] \leftarrow$  randomly generated individual;
11     $P_{new}[j].replaced \leftarrow true$ ;
12  else
13     $P_{new}[j] \leftarrow P[j]$ ;
14  end
15 end
16 return  $P_{new}$  ;
```

Algorithm 3: Agents

```
1 initializeParameters(grid);
2 initializeParameters(agents);
3 while stopping condition is not met do
4   foreach agent in grid do
5     if there is a better cell in neighborhood(agent) then
6       | agent.position  $\leftarrow$  best cell in neighborhood(agent);
7     else
8       | agent.position  $\leftarrow$  random cell in neighborhood(agent);
9     end
10    prevSolution  $\leftarrow$  solution at agent.position;
11    currentSolution  $\leftarrow$ 
12    alterSolution(prevSolution, perturbationRadius);
13    if currentSolution got improved then
14      | solution at agent.position  $\leftarrow$  currentSolution;
15      | bestSolution  $\leftarrow$  currentSolution;
16    end
17  end
end
```

Table 1: Parameter settings for the SORIGA algorithm

Parameter	Value
Population size	50
Elite size	2
Replacement rate (r_r)	0.02
Mutation rate (r_m)	0.01
Crossover rate (r_c)	0.7
α (for the BLX- α operator)	1.0

every agent moves to the best grid-neighbor solution and tries to improve it. To do that, the function *alterSolution()* is called (line 11 of the pseudocode) to generate a new random solution inside a hypersphere of radius *perturbationRadius* around the original solution. The previous solution is replaced with the new one if the improvement succeeds.

The Agents algorithm can be seen as a population-based decentralized cooperative algorithm, since the improvements of an agent are immediately available to the others. When an agent is moving to the best neighbor solution of the grid, it will be attracted by good grid cell solutions that were stored by other agents. Therefore, as the agents move through the grid, they will tend to act on those cells that other agents have already improved.

Table 2: Parameter settings for the Agents algorithm

Parameter	Value
Number of rows	5
Number of columns	10
Number of agents	4
Perturbation radius	14% of x range

The parameter settings used in the experimentation for the Agents algorithm are summarized in Table 2, and were determined by a brief trial and error process conducted by the authors using their own expertise on tuning this algorithm, departing from the settings used in [20, 21].

2.3. The mQSO (standard approach)

The mQSO [3] is a variant of the classical PSO [11] algorithm, developed by Blackwell and Branke to specifically cope with DOP's.

A swarm in the mQSO is formed by two types of particles:

- *Trajectory* particles (also known as *classical* or *neutral*). These are the particles used by the canonical PSO algorithm, which positions are updated following the usual movement equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{a}(t+1) &= \chi[\eta_1 c_1(\mathbf{x}_{pbest} - \mathbf{x}(t)) \\ &\quad + \eta_2 c_2(\mathbf{x}_{gbest} - \mathbf{x}(t))] \\ &\quad - (1 - \chi)\mathbf{v}(t) \\ \mathbf{v}(t+1) &= \mathbf{v}(t) + \mathbf{a}(t+1) \\ \mathbf{x}(t+1) &= \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{v}(t+1)\end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{a} are position, velocity and acceleration vectors respectively. \mathbf{x}_{pbest} is the best so far position discovered by each particle, and \mathbf{x}_{gbest} is the best so far position discovered by the whole swarm. Parameters $\eta_1, \eta_2 > 2$ are spring constants, and c_1 and c_2 are random numbers in the interval $[0.0, 1.0]$. Since particle movement must progressively contract in order to converge, a constriction factor χ , $\chi < 1$ is used, as defined by Clerc and Kennedy in [26]. This factor replaces other slowing approaches in the literature, such as inertial weight and velocity clamping [27].

- *Quantum* particles. These particles were newly introduced in the mQSO algorithm, and aim at reaching a higher level of diversity by moving randomly within a hypersphere of radius \mathbf{r} centered on \mathbf{x}_{gbest} . This random movement is performed according to a probability distribution over the hypersphere, in this case, a uniform distribution:

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \mathbf{rand}_{hypersphere}(\mathbf{x}_{gbest}, \mathbf{r})$$

Beside this, the general idea of the mQSO is to use a set of multiple swarms that simultaneously explore the search space. This multi-swarm approach has the purpose of maintaining the diversity, in addition to the use of quantum particles. This is a key point for DOP's, since the optimum can change at any time, and the algorithm must be able to react and find a new optimum. In order to prevent

several swarms from competing over the same area, an inter-swarm exclusion mechanism is also used, randomizing the worst swarm whenever two of them are too close.

Table 3: Parameter settings for all mQSO variants

Parameter	mqso	mqso-change	mqso-rand	mqso-both
Number of swarms	5			
Number of particles/swarm	10			
Number of q-particles	2	variable	2	variable
Number of t-particles	8	variable	8	variable
c_1, c_2	2.05 (as recommended in [26])			
χ	0.729843788 (as recommended in [26])			
q-particles radius	12% of x range			
Inter-swarm exclusion distance	1.2% of x range			

The parameter settings used in the standard mQSO are summarized in Table 3. Please note that the variants of the mQSO that use heuristic rules (Sects. 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6) share most of these settings, with the exception of the t-q particles ratio, a fact that is also reflected in the table. These settings are based on the standard ones used in the literature, defined in [3] and [26]. Also note that the mQSO was originally tested only in the MPB, and therefore, some of the settings were specifically designed for that problem. In order to adapt to the other problems tested (Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin), the q-particles and inter-swarm exclusion distance have been changed from 12 and 1.2 (absolute units), to 12% and 1.2% of the problem’s solution space range (relative units).

2.4. The mQSO + Change Rule

In [28] it was shown that the *trajectory* and *quantum* particles of the mQSO contributed differently to their swarm’s *gbest*, depending on how much time had elapsed since the last change in the environment.

It was observed that trajectory particles are more likely to find better solutions than quantum particles through all the execution. Additionally, the experiments show that right after a change, trajectory particles tend to contribute to the best of a swarm 60% of the times (we denote this proportion as α), while the quantum particles contribute the remaining 40% ($1 - \alpha$). These differences are maintained

for a short period of time (θ_d , diversity period), and then slowly increase until they stabilize to 80% for trajectory particles (β), and 20% for quantum particles ($1 - \beta$), for the rest of the execution until the next change (θ_c , convergence period). This behavior is reasonable, since quantum particles move randomly and are better suited for increasing diversity, which is more necessary, precisely, right after a change in the environment. See Fig. 1 for a graphical explanation of these concepts.

The Change Rule adjusts the proportions of each particle type according to an approximation of their expected performance, as observed in the previous experiments. This is summarized in the following statement:

IF a change in the environment has occurred recently

THEN temporarily increase the number of *quantum* particles of a swarm and decrease the number of *trajectory* particles

Figure 1: This figure shows the contribution of each particle type to the *gbest* of a swarm, and illustrates the concepts used in the Change Rule (θ , θ_d , θ_c , α and β) giving a graphical explanation for the chosen values.

Finally, we experimentally estimated that, in order for the quantum particles to result beneficial after a change, a minimum of 5 iterations were needed (i.e., θ_d 's minimum value should be 5, which implies that θ should be at least 34 iterations). If θ_d is determined to be less than 5 iterations, the rule is disabled, leaving the algorithm as a standard mQSO.

Table 4: Parameter settings for Change Rule

Parameter	Value
θ_d	15% of total duration of θ
θ_d min. duration	5 iterations
θ_c	85% of total duration of θ
α	0.6
β	0.8

These settings are summarized in Table 4, and extend the ones shown in Table 3, which are also applied to this method.

2.5. The mQSO + Rand Rule

This rule was originally designed for preventing poorly performing swarms from consuming function evaluations that lead them to no improvement, or that could be better used by other swarms. The rule can be summarized as follows:

IF	a swarm is performing <i>badly</i>
THEN	relocate the swarm randomly or pause it if there is not enough time

A way of determining that a swarm has a bad performance is to compare its fitness with the rest of the swarms: if it is among the worst, then it has a bad performance. However, a swarm may be performing badly for many reasons, not all of them being necessarily punishable (fluctuations in the fitness due to the random nature of the mQSO algorithm, the swarm is still in a search process and has not yet converged, etc). Ideally, only swarms which are in *bad* zones of the search space should be relocated. In order to prevent a swarm in a possible good zone from being relocated due to temporary low fitness situations, additional conditions must be met.

First, the low fitness situation should be maintained for a certain number of consecutive iterations. If a swarm is among the worst ones only once, it may be bad luck, but if it is repeatedly among the worst ones, then there is a chance that the swarm is in a bad zone.

Second, it is necessary to check if a swarm has converged. A swarm in a search-around phase may have a low fitness, but it still has room for improvement.

On the other hand, an already converged swarm with low fitness is more likely to be stuck in a bad zone. The way in which convergence is detected for each swarm in this rule is based on the swarm's improvement ratio. The improvement of a swarm is defined as the difference between the current fitness and the fitness of the previous iteration. When a swarm is searching and has not converged, it usually makes great improvements in the fitness from one iteration to another. Obviously, there may be iterations in which the improvement is low, or even nonexistent, due to the random nature of the search. However, this low improvement situation is unlikely, and usually does not last for too long. On the other hand, if a swarm has converged close to a local optimum, it will make very small improvements, if any, from one iteration to the next one. An example of this behavior is shown in Figure 2. Therefore, if the improvement ratio of a swarm descends below a certain percentage of its maximum improvement since the last change, it is a good indicative that it has converged.

Figure 2: Evolution of the fitness and improvement of two swarms (f_1 and f_2) from a convergence point of view. At $t = t_1$, $f_2 > f_1$. However, once the swarms have converged, at $t = t_2$, $f_1 > f_2$ (darker area, $t \geq t_{conv}$). Convergence is detected based on the improvement: if improvement descends below a certain threshold (here, chosen to be 15% of maximum improvement, i.e., $I_{conv} \leq I_{max} \cdot 0.15$), the swarm is considered to have converged.

If we combine all these conditions (being among the worst swarms, for a certain number of consecutive iterations, with a low improvement rate that indicates that the swarm has converged), it is very likely that the swarm is indeed located in a bad zone. In this case, there is no point in wasting more function evaluations

in that zone, and the swarm should be better relocated. An special case is when the algorithm is able to predict when changes in the environment will happen, and the next change is very close. In this case, relocating the swarm may be useless, since there may not be enough time for the swarm to converge. The swarm is then temporarily *paused* and the rest of the swarms have more iterations to improve their results. Therefore, the rule can be re-stated as:

IF a swarm’s fitness is among the worst **AND**
this situation lasts for several consecutive iterations **AND**
the swarm has converged

THEN relocate the swarm randomly or pause it if there is not enough time

The pseudocode for the rule’s behavior is presented in Algorithm 4. The parameter settings are summarized in Table 5, and extend the ones shown in Table 3, which are also applied to this method.

As a final comment, the Rand Rule requires that a swarm is considered to be among the worst for at least 5 consecutive iterations. This in practice means, as it also happened with the Change Rule, that it will be disabled for low change period scenarios: if the environment changes too fast, the swarms will not have enough time to converge and the rule will not be applied, leaving the mQSO + Rand Rule as a standard mQSO for these cases.

2.6. The mQSO + Both Rules

Finally, a third rule was used, which combines the previous ones (Change Rule and Rand Rule). This combination is very simple: just check if any of the rules can be applied, and if so, do it.

The experiments performed so far suggest that the rules do not reinforce each other [19] and the mQSO + Both Rules is less effective than any of them separately. However, the use of both rules may still provide stability and homogeneity to the performance of the mQSO under some problem configurations. Therefore, this rule still qualifies as worth studying for the experiments.

This rule uses the same settings as the Change Rule and Rand Rule combined, which can be seen in their corresponding parameter settings tables (Tables 4 and 5).

Algorithm 4: Rand Rule pseudocode

```
1 minImprovement  $\leftarrow$  15% of swarm's maximum since last change ;
2 maxCount  $\leftarrow$  5 ;
3 minRemainingTime  $\leftarrow$  20% of  $\theta$  ;
4 if improvement < minImprovement then
5   | count ++;
6   | if count  $\geq$  maxCount then
7     |   if fitness of swarm's best particle among worst 20% of all swarms
8       |   then
9         |   | if remaining time until next change < minRemainingTime
10        |   | then
11          |   | | pause swarm ;
12          |   | else
13            |   | | reposition swarm randomly ;
14            |   | end
15          |   | end
16        |   | end
17      |   end
18    | end
19  | else
20    | count  $\leftarrow$  0;
21  | end
```

Table 5: Parameter settings for Rand Rule

Parameter	Value
Min. improvement ratio	15% of historical maximum
Max. low improvement count	5
Percentage for <i>bad</i> performance	20%
Min. available time	20% of total duration of θ

2.7. Trajectory-Based Centralised Cooperative Strategy

This centralised multi-threaded cooperative strategy based on trajectory heuristics has been recently applied with success to DOPs [22, 23, 29]. In this section, we describe the main aspects of the strategy and the more important points for the purposes of the paper. Further details can be obtained in the previous references.

The strategy consists in a set of solvers/threads, where each solver can implement the same or a different heuristic to deal with the problem. The coordinator processes the information received from them and produces subsequent adjustments of their behaviour by sending “orders”. To achieve this exchange of data, a blackboard model is used [30]. Concretely, two blackboards are available, one where the solvers write the reports of their performance and the coordinator reads them, and another, where the orders are written by the coordinator and read by the solvers.

In this strategy, after the initialisation stage, the solvers are executed asynchronously while sending and receiving information. The coordinator checks through the input blackboard which solver provided new information and decides whether its behaviour needs to be adapted using a rule base. If so, it will calculate a new behaviour which will be sent to the solvers through the output blackboard. As for the solvers, its working is also very simple: once execution has begun, performance information is sent and adaptation orders from the coordinator are received alternatively.

The information flow in this strategy can be divided in the following three steps: 1) performance information is sent from the solvers to the coordinator, 2) this information is processed and stored by the coordinator and 3) coordinator sends directives to the threads. In the data flow solvers \Rightarrow coordinator, each report contains the next items:

- Solver identification

- A time stamp t
- The best solution found until that time by this solver s_{best}
- A list with the local minima found by the method since the last report

The list of local minima is processed by the coordinator that keeps a list with all local optima found by the solvers named Visited Region List (VRL). Actually, the local minima are considered as the regions defined by a hypersphere with radius ρ and centre in the points stored in the VRL. Each entry of the VRL also maintains a register φ with the visiting frequency of that region by any search thread.

The behaviour of the solvers is controlled by a set of rules of the form *if condition then action*. These rules allow the coordinator to determine if a solver is behaving correctly as well as the action that should be performed to correct such behavior.

To deal with DOPs, the strategy checks when the fitness function changes, on one hand, and restarts those memories that do not contain relevant information for the new search space, on the other hand. These issues are handled in both the coordinator and solver sides through a local counter of the number of fitness changes detected on each thread. If the counter of detected fitness changes differs between a solver and the coordinator, the higher counter is communicated and the search process is adapted accordingly.

In this work, we have considered two versions of the strategy with different control rule bases:

- **independent**: there is no cooperation, that is, the solvers are run independently without exchanging information among them.
- **reactive**: composed by only one rule whose design is based on Reactive Search ideas [31] and was previously presented in [22]. Its definition is the following:

<p>IF φ of the last local minimum visited by $solver_i$ is bigger than $\lambda_{reaction}$</p> <p>THEN send the best global solution perturbed by degree ϕ</p>

The threshold $\lambda_{reaction}$ regulates the activation of the rule. ϕ is given by the next formula:

$$\phi = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \varphi - \lambda_{reaction} \leq 0 \\ \varphi - \lambda_{reaction}, & \text{if } \varphi - \lambda_{reaction} > 0 \text{ and} \\ & \varphi - \lambda_{reaction} < \phi_{max} \\ \phi_{max}, & \text{if } \varphi - \lambda_{reaction} \geq \phi_{max} \end{cases}$$

$\lambda_{reaction}$ establishes when a higher perturbation than the basic one ($\phi = 0$) is applied and ϕ_{max} is the maximum degree. This perturbation is done by means of a mutation operator that consists in randomly selecting a direction following a uniform distribution and then, take the point at a distance r from the best global solution. The higher the value of ϕ , the bigger the distance r .

Both versions of the strategy are composed by 12 solvers that implement a tabu search algorithm with different parameter instantiations. The parameter settings for these methods were chosen according to the original ones reported by the authors in the corresponding paper, and are summarized in Table 6. For a deeper explanation on the cooperative strategies, the tabu search solvers, and the parameters, the interested reader is referred to [22, 23].

Table 6: Parameter setting for the cooperative strategies.

Parameter	Value
number of tabu search solvers	12
distance to best global solution in mutation operator (r)	1% of x range
antecedent threshold ($\lambda_{reaction}$)	1
visited regions radius (ρ)	15% of x range

3. Benchmark functions for Dynamic Optimization Problems

3.1. The Moving Peaks Benchmark

The MPB is a test benchmark for DOP's originally proposed in [1]. It is a maximization problem consisting in the superposition of m peaks, each one characterized by its own height (h), width (w), and location of its centre (p). The fitness function of the MPB is defined as follows:

$$\text{MPB}(\mathbf{x}) = \max_j \left(h^j - w^j \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - p_i^j)^2} \right), j = 1, \dots, m \quad (1)$$

where n is the dimensionality of the problem. The highest point of each peak corresponds to its centre, and therefore, the global optimum is the centre of the peak with the highest parameter \mathbf{h} .

Dynamism is introduced in the MPB by periodically changing the parameters of each peak j after a certain number of function evaluations (ω):

$$\mathbf{h}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{h}_j(t) + \mathbf{h}_s \cdot \mathbf{N}(0, 1) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{w}_j(t) + \mathbf{w}_s \cdot \mathbf{N}(0, 1) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{p}_j(t) + \mathbf{v}_j(t+1) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_j(t+1) = \frac{\mathbf{s}}{|\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{v}_j(t)|} ((1 - \lambda)\mathbf{r} + \lambda\mathbf{v}_j(t)) \quad (5)$$

Changes to both width and height parameters depend on a given severity for each of them (\mathbf{w}_s and \mathbf{h}_s). Changes to the centre position depend on a shift vector $\mathbf{v}_j(t+1)$, which is a linear combination of a random vector \mathbf{r} and the previous shift vector $\mathbf{v}_j(t)$ for the peak, normalized to length s (position severity, shift distance, or simply *severity*). The random vector \mathbf{r} is created by drawing random numbers for each dimension and normalizing its length to s . Finally, parameter λ indicates the linear correlation with respect to the previous shift, where a value of 1 indicates “total correlation” and a value of 0 “pure randomness”.

The MPB has been widely used as a test suite for different algorithms under the presence of dynamism. One of the most used configurations for this purpose is Scenario 2, which is described in the web site of the MPB ¹, and consists of the set of parameters indicated in Table 7. This scenario has also been used as the base configuration for some of the experiments conducted in this work, as it will be explained in Sect. 4.1.

3.2. Multimodal continuous functions

The rest of the testing benchmarks of the experiments are based on standard multimodal functions commonly used in static continuous optimization problems.

¹<http://www.aifb.uni-karlsruhe.de/~jbr/MovPeaks/>

Table 7: Standard settings for the Scenario 2 of the Moving Peaks Benchmark

Parameter	Value
Number of peaks (m)	$\in [10, 200]$
Number of dimensions (n)	5
x range	$[0, 100]^n$
Peak heights (h_j)	$\in [30, 70]$
Peak widths (w_j)	$\in [1, 12]$
Change period (ω)	5000
Height severity (h_s)	7.0
Width severity (w_s)	1.0
Severity (s)	$\in [0.0, 3.0]$
Correlation coefficient (λ)	$\in [0.0, 1.0]$

Three functions have been chosen, Ackley, Griewank, and Rastrigin, and their equations are shown below:

$$\mathbf{Ackley}(\mathbf{x}) = -20 \exp \left(-0.2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(2\pi x_i) \right) + 20 + e \quad (6)$$

$$x \in [-32, 32], \quad x^* = 0^n$$

$$\mathbf{Griewank}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{4000} - \prod_{i=1}^n \cos \left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{i}} \right) + 1 \quad (7)$$

$$x \in [-50, 50], \quad x^* = 0^n$$

$$\mathbf{Rastrigin}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i) + 10) \quad (8)$$

$$x \in [-5, 5], \quad x^* = 0^n$$

where n is the dimensionality of the problem, and x^* is the optimum (in all the

functions, the optimum is located at the origin of coordinates, the 0^n position). A visualization of these functions and the MPB, for the 2-dimensional case, is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: A 3D visualization of the MPB, Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions.

In order to adapt these functions to DOP's, the origin of coordinates is explicitly introduced as a parameter, \mathbf{p} , through the following expression:

$$f'(x) = f(x - \mathbf{p})$$

$$f \in \{Ackley, Griewank, Rastrigin\}$$

Then, dynamism is introduced like in the MPB, by periodically changing the origin of coordinates \mathbf{p} using the previously defined equations 4 and 5. Therefore, parameters *change period* and *severity* are also applied to these problems.

4. Design of experiments

4.1. Parameter settings for the benchmarks

Based on the experience of the authors, some of the parameters of a DOP that affect more the performance of algorithms are *dimensionality*, *change period*, and

severity of the change.

In the experiments conducted in this work, a set of different values for each of the three previous parameters were selected, and a full factorial experimental design was used, meaning that all possible combinations of the parameter values were tested, for every problem, and every algorithm.

As it has been previously mentioned, the Scenario 2 of the MPB has been used as a baseline configuration for the experiments, in order to keep the results related with the existing literature. Therefore, the set of values for the parameters were explicitly chosen to contain a value within the range of those defined by Scenario 2. The complete set of parameter values is listed below, where the bold-faced value indicates the one that corresponds to the Scenario 2 settings:

- dimensionality: {**5**, 10, 15, 20, 25}
- change period factors {40, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, 800, 900, **1000**}
- severity {**2%**, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10%, 12%, 14%, 16%, 18%, 20%}

The change period parameter indicates how many function evaluations is the algorithm allowed to consume before a change in the environment occurs. However, it is well-known that dimensionality affects the ability of an algorithm to optimize a function: the higher the dimensionality of the problem, the lower the performance. Therefore, instead of fixing the number of function evaluations allowed for a certain configuration independently of the dimensionality, we consider the change period as a *factor*: the final change period value is obtained multiplying the change period factor by the dimensionality.

Also, severity depends on the range of the input variable x (all x_i dimensions have the same range in the benchmarks), but this range is different for each problem. In order to unify test configurations, instead of using absolute severity values, a percentage of x 's range is used.

The final test configurations for all problems is summarized in Table 8.

4.2. Performance measure

There are several performance measures used for DOP's in the literature (see, for example, [7, 32, 33]). In order to make our results comparable with other closely related works, the performance measure selected for our experiments was

Table 8: Experiment settings for the MPB, Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions

Parameter	MPB	Ackley	Griewank	Rastrigin
Number of dimensions (n)	{5, 10, 15, 20, 25}			
Change period (ω)	{40, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, 800, 900, 1000} · n			
x range	$[0, 100]^n$	$[-32, 32]^n$	$[-50, 50]^n$	$[-5, 5]^n$
Severity (s)	{2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10%, 12%, 14%, 16%, 18%, 20%} · x range			
Correlation coefficient (λ)	0.5			
Number of peaks (m)	100	-	-	-
Peak heights (h_j)	rand [30, 70]	-	-	-
Peak widths (w_j)	rand [1, 12]	-	-	-
Height severity (h_s)	7.0	-	-	-
Width severity (w_s)	1.0	-	-	-

the *offline error* (e_{off}) [7]. This measure is the average of the error of the best solution found by the algorithm since the last change, for every function evaluation, and for all changes:

$$e_{off} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \frac{1}{N_e(i)} \sum_{j=1}^{N_e(i)} (f_i^* - f_{ij}) \quad (9)$$

where N_c is the total number of changes in the environment, $N_e(i)$ is the total number of evaluations allowed in the i -th change, f_i^* is the optimum value of the i -th change, and f_{ij} is the best value found by the algorithm since the beginning of the i -th change up to the j -th evaluation. Since changes in the environment are produced at a fixed rate (i.e., $N_e(i) = N_e, \forall i$), the equation can be simplified as follows:

$$e_{off} = \frac{1}{N_c N_e} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_e} (f_i^* - f_{ij}) \quad (10)$$

The execution of an algorithm for N_c changes is defined as a *run*. In order to obtain statistically meaningful results, each experiment consisted of N_r independent runs, each one with a different random seed. In this work, we have chosen

$N_r = 50$, and the comparison of the algorithms has been performed using those 50 e_{off} measures for each algorithm.

4.3. Ranking method

From Table 8 we can calculate the number of configurations to test for every problem. If we also consider all the problems and algorithms, we obtain the total amount of experiments to perform:

$$\begin{aligned} 5 \text{ dimensions} \times 11 \text{ change freq.} \times 10 \text{ severities} &= 550 \text{ configurations} \\ 550 \text{ configurations} \times 8 \text{ algorithms} \times 4 \text{ problems} &= 17600 \text{ experiments} \end{aligned}$$

Due to the high number of experiments, it is almost impossible to show all the numerical results of the algorithms in a comprehensive way using tables. In order to overcome this, we need to compact the information to be displayed, and present it in a more manageable format. Recall that we want to provide an overview of the behaviour and we are not searching for the “best” algorithm. For this purpose, we use a technique named SRCS, introduced by the authors in [34]. SRCS focuses on creating a ranking of all the algorithms, instead of displaying the absolute performance values of each one. The algorithms are ranked from best performing to worst performing on every configuration according to the number of methods they significantly improve using statistical tests. After that, a color key is associated to each rank value in order to present the results visually. With the color scheme currently used by SRCS, a lighter color indicates a higher ranking, and therefore, a better performance. This idea is illustrated in Fig. 4, using actual performance results on MPB’s Scenario 2 configuration. These rank colors can then be used instead of numerical values, thus allowing to better compress the information to be displayed when presenting multiple problems / multiple configurations / multiple algorithms results.

The details of the SRCS technique are as follows. For each problem configuration, the N_r values of the e_{off} of each algorithm are compared using statistical tests (in the experiments, $N_r = 50$). As recommended in [35, 36], non-parametric tests are used, first checking for differences among the results of *all* algorithms using a Kruskal-Wallis (KW) test. If there is enough evidence for overall statistical differences, then a test is performed to assess individual differences among each pair of algorithms. In this case, a Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon (MWW) test is used, with Holm’s correction to compensate for multiple comparisons. In both tests, the significance level used is 0.05. If the test concludes that there is enough evidence

Figure 4: Ranking and color scheme of the algorithms for the Scenario 2 of the MPB ($dimensions = 5$, $change\ period\ factor = 1000$, $severity = 2\%$). The boxplot shows the distribution of the 50 values of the e_{off} for every algorithm, ordered by its mean value. Dotted rectangles indicate those algorithms for which no statistical differences were found at a significance level of 0.05 ($reactivecs/independentcs$, and $independentcs/mqsoboth$). The table on the right displays, for every algorithm, how many times it shows a significantly better performance (“better than”), no significant differences (“equal to”) or significantly worse performance (“worse than”) when it is compared with respect to the other 7 algorithms, and its final rank with the correspondent color key.

for statistical differences, the algorithm with the lowest average e_{off} (the best one) adds 1 to its rank, and the other adds -1. In case of a tie (no statistical differences at 0.05 significance level), both algorithms receive a 0 (no addition nor subtraction to their rank). This procedure is summarized in Algorithm 5, where both *Kruskal-Wallis* and *Wilcoxon* functions are assumed to return the p-value of the test. Once the ranks of the algorithms for all the configurations are obtained, the results are grouped in matrices, and the numerical values of the ranks are replaced by their color keys (see the experiments' results in Sect. 5).

Algorithm 5: Ranking(*results*, *algorithms*)

```

1 for each algorithm in algorithms do
2   | ranking[algorithm]  $\leftarrow$  0;
3 end

4 p-value-kw  $\leftarrow$  Kruskal-Wallis(results);
5 if p-value-kw < 0.05 then
6   | p-values-mww  $\leftarrow$  Wilcoxon(results, "Holm");
7   | // Consider each pair of algorithms avoiding
8   | // repetitions
9   | // (i.e., [a1, a2] = [a2, a1])
10  | for each pair (algorithm1, algorithm2) in algorithms do
11  |   | if p-values-mww[algorithm1][algorithm2] < 0.05 then
12  |   |   | if mean(results[algorithm1]) < mean(results[algorithm2])
13  |   |   |   | then
14  |   |   |   |   | ranking[algorithm1] ++;
15  |   |   |   |   | ranking[algorithm2] --;
16  |   |   |   |   | else
17  |   |   |   |   |   | ranking[algorithm1] --;
18  |   |   |   |   |   | ranking[algorithm2] ++;
19  |   |   |   |   | end
20  |   |   |   | end
21  |   |   | end
22  |   | end
23  | end
24 return ranking

```

The main advantages of this method are:

- It is able to compress a lot of the numerical information of the results and

present it in a visual way, which is more meaningful to humans.

- Rankings are also meaningful *per se*, since positive ranks indicate “above the average” algorithms for a given configuration, while negative ones indicate “below the average”.
- Moreover, the final numerical rank for an algorithm indicates “how many other algorithms it is better than” (there is statistical evidence for a significantly better performance).
- Finally, this compressed, visual way of presenting the results not only allows to clearly identify the best and worst performing algorithms, but also to perform an overall analysis of the behavior of these methods over several environmental conditions.

However, SRCS, as any technique, has disadvantages that need to be considered. The main drawback is that the ranking is a relative measure instead of an absolute one: if a new algorithm is introduced for comparing, the whole ranking needs to be recalculated. The good news is that, as long as the original e_{off} values for each algorithm are kept, recalculating the rankings is a rather simple and fast process.

4.4. Comments on statistical issues for the SRCS technique

Finally, a comment on the number of independent repetitions for each experiment (N_r) and other issues relating statistical tests. It is generally accepted by the research community in the DOP area that the higher the number of these repetitions, the smaller the differences that a statistical test detects, which may lead to considering some differences as significant, when, in fact, they are not. This is an incomplete interpretation that may lead to erroneous statements.

When a MWW test is performed between two samples (i.e., the N_r results of two algorithms for a given configuration, in our context), the test attempts to determine if the two samples are statistically unequal, rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 of statistical equality. This is generally reported by the test in the form of a *p-value*, i.e., the probability of obtaining the actually observed differences in the two samples if the null hypothesis H_0 were true. Generally, one rejects H_0 if the *p-value* is smaller than a pre-fixed significance level α (e.g., 0.05). Moreover, if the two samples are concluded to be statistically unequal, the MWW test is able to estimate the magnitude of the difference, in absolute units (this is called the *effect size*).

When comparing results of two algorithms, it is very unlikely that the obtained samples are statistically equal, even if the two algorithms are very similar. There will always be differences, even if these differences are small. However, detecting those differences may require higher sample sizes at a given significance level. Quoting Vargha and Delaney [37]:

[...] if population 1 and 2 are stochastically unequal, then at any fixed α level of significance the probability of the MWW test being significant at the α level tends to 1 as the m, n sample size values tend to infinity. By contrast, if populations 1 and 2 are stochastically equal, then the probability of the MWW test being significant at the α level will not tend to 1, however large the two samples be.

For example, suppose that the true difference between two algorithms' results is 1.5 performance units. Using 10 repetitions (sample size = 10) for each sample may not allow a MWW test to detect such differences at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. In this case, the test will conclude that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. However, using 50 repetitions (sample size = 50), the MWW may now be able to detect the differences at the same $\alpha = 0.05$ level, concluding that there are statistically significant differences.

Therefore, it is true that increasing the number of repetitions of an experiment may lead to a statistical test concluding that there are differences. However, this is not a flaw in the design of the experiment, but a sign of higher precision of the test. Think of it as if looking for differences between two physical objects using your naked eye (e.g., sample size = 10), or using a microscope (e.g., sample size = 50).

This leads to the distinction between *statistically* significant differences and *practical* significant differences. It should be an objective of an experiment design to gather as much data as possible to make any difference *statistically* significant. On top of it, it should be the researcher's responsibility to decide if these differences are of *practical* interest. But this cannot be properly done if there is not enough statistical evidence to support the conclusion. For example, a MWW test using a sample size of 50, may be able to detect a difference between two algorithms of 1.5 units. The researcher, on the other hand, may decide that a difference of practical interest should be of at least 5 units, and that therefore, there are no *practical* differences between the two samples. However, if there is not enough statistical evidence due to a small sample size, the researcher cannot be sure if there are really no differences, small differences of no practical interest, or differences of practical interest.

As a rule of thumb, any experiment should gather as much data as possible in order to guarantee safe practical conclusions, and only be limited by practical issues like computational effort, time requirements, etc.

The experiments conducted in this paper were performed on synthetic test benchmarks, i.e., they are not real-world problems, so no practical differences could be established a priori. Therefore, any *statistically* significant difference was also considered of *practical* significance. The limit of $N_r = 50$ was arbitrarily chosen to be high enough to provide reasonable evidence without too much computational effort (remember that 17600 experiments were run, and each of them was repeated N_r independent times).

For more in-depth information about the use of non-parametric tests and questions on the factors that determine them, the interested reader is referred to [38–40].

5. Experimental results

The results of the experiments are presented in the form of 4 figures arranged as tables (Figs. 5, 6, 7, and 8). Each one corresponds to a problem, and shows the ranking results (as explained in Sect. 4.3) of the algorithms for all the configurations of that problem. Each row corresponds to the results of a given algorithm, and each column to the results of a given dimensionality of the problem. Cells show the results of all change period vs. severity configurations, for that algorithm (row) and dimensionality (column).

Results for the MPB problem are shown in Fig. 5, for the Ackley problem in Fig. 6, for the Griewank problem in Fig. 7, and finally, for the Rastrigin problem in Fig. 8.

5.1. Analysis of the MPB results

The results of the MPB experiments (Fig. 5) show, for the 5-dimensional case, that the *mqso-rand* algorithm clearly dominates the rest. Only in the case of low change period factor it is paired with the results of the other mQSO versions. This is explained by the fact that the Rand rule is disabled for these change frequencies (remember that the rule needs a minimum of 5 iterations to fire). Actually, for the case of a change period factor of 40, all the rules are disabled, and therefore, all the mQSO versions obtain the same results and ranks.

For 10 dimensions, the results are similar to those obtained in the 5-dimensional case, except for the emergent success of the *agents* and the *reactive-cs* algorithms.

Figure 5: Rank results of all the algorithms for the MPB. See section 4.3 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

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Figure 6: Rank results of all the algorithms for the **Ackley** function. See section 4.3 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

Figure 7: Rank results of all the algorithms for the **Griewank** function. See section 4.3 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

Figure 8: Rank results of all the algorithms for the **Rastrigin** function. See section 4.3 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

The *reactive-cs* starts to dominate in the upper-left corner of the results, corresponding to the low severity ($\sim 2\%$), high change period factor (~ 1000). The *agents*, on the other hand, starts to get good results for high severities.

The 15-dimensional case is an inflexion point that marks the change between the dominance of the *mqso-rand* algorithm and the *agents* algorithm. The *agents* algorithm obtains now the best results for high severity configurations, while the *reactive-cs* keeps on dominating the low severity, high change period corner. The *mqso-rand* now only obtains good results for a small, fuzzy region of medium severity, medium change period.

Finally, for the 20- and 25-dimensional case, the results are almost identical, with the *agents* dominating all the configurations except for a small region of low severity. The *reactive-cs* gets first on these low severity configurations, and obtains remarkable results for the rest, paired with the *independent-cs*.

An additional comment must be done to emphasize the results of the SORIGA algorithm. Although they are bad in general terms, the algorithm seems to behave interestingly good for very low change period factor configurations. This will prove to be a characteristic feature of this algorithm by its results on the other benchmarks.

5.2. Analysis of the Ackley results

The results for the Ackley experiments (Fig. 6) show a clear dominance of the cooperative strategies over the rest, unlike what happened in the MPB. Both the *independent-cs* and *reactive-cs* algorithms perform very good in all configurations, being always in the first or second rank positions.

The only algorithm that is able to compete with them is SORIGA, for low and medium change period configurations. The results start to become good for the 10-dimensional case, with its best results for 15 dimensions, and then slowly getting back for higher dimensions. Although SORIGA had bad results in the MPB, it already exhibited a tendency for good performance on low change period factors, which is confirmed in the Ackley experiments.

For this problem, the best performing variant of the mQSO is the *mqso-both* for dimensionality higher than 5, and the *mqso-rand* for the 5-dimensional case.

Also, unlike what happened with the MPB, the rankings are fairly uniform over all dimensions for a given algorithm: those with a bad ranking remain bad, and those with good ranking stay good. This does not necessarily imply that the algorithms are very stable on this problem. It could simply be explained by the clear dominance of the cooperative strategies, which, from a ranking point of

view, could smooth the results due to the differences between the firsts ranks and the rest.

5.3. Analysis of the Griewank results

The results for the Griewank experiments (Fig. 7) can only confirm the absolute dominance of the cooperative strategies over the rest on all configurations. Only SORIGA obtain good results for low change period factors on the 5-dimensional case. Between the cooperative strategies, the *reactive-cs* seems to be slightly better than *independent-cs*, mainly for high change period factors. This indicates that, if the strategies have enough time to search, the *reactive-cs* obtain better results.

In general, the results confirm the tendencies that were observed in the other experiments for some algorithms: SORIGA is better for very low change period factors, and the *agents* is better for medium and high severities. Among the mQSO variants, the best performing are the standard *mqso* and *mqso-change*.

5.4. Analysis of the Rastrigin results

The results for the Rastrigin experiments (Fig. 8) mainly draw the same conclusions than for the Griewank experiments: cooperative strategies are clearly superior than the rest, with the *reactive-cs* slightly better than *independent-cs* for high change period factors.

SORIGA still performs well, with its characteristic tendency of obtaining better results for low change frequencies. The *agents* surprisingly performs quite bad, being the worst algorithm for most configurations. Among the mQSO variants, the standard *mqso* obtains fairly good results for the 5-dimensional case, and for higher dimensions, the *mqso-both* is reasonably stable on most configurations.

5.5. Global analysis of the results

A global overview of the results obtained in the experiments allows to get some general insights of the behaviors of the algorithms.

The first conclusion is that there are very big differences between the results of the MPB and those of the other problems. In the Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin problems, the cooperative strategies greatly outperform the other algorithms, while in the MPB, there is no algorithm which clearly dominates the rest. In the MPB, this favours the emergence of “performance niches” where some algorithms are better than the others for some configurations. This is probably related with the inner structure of the local optima distribution of this problem. In the Ackley,

Griewank and Rastrigin functions, the optima are distributed with a certain pattern. Moreover, when the environment changes, the fitness function is shifted, but the structure of the local optima distribution remains the same. In the MPB, however, the local optima correspond to the peaks, which are randomly distributed, and each one is moved independently of the others when the environment changes (see Fig. 3 for a visual idea of each problem’s fitness landscape).

The SORIGA algorithm, in general, seems to behave better for rapidly changing environments (i.e., very low change period factors, ~ 40), independently of the problem.

The *agents* algorithm, on the contrary, seems to obtain better results for medium and high severity. Since the severity affects the degree of randomization that a change in the environment produces (high severity shifts the landscapes so much that it can even be considered a new random environment), this can explain why the *agents* algorithm behaves better for the MPB problem.

The cooperative strategies obtain the best results for the Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions. As it have been said, this could be caused by the inner structure of the local optima distribution of each problem. This is specially true for the Griewank and Rastrigin functions, which have small differences among local maxima and minima, making their fitness landscape very homogeneous (see Fig. 3). The ability of the cooperative strategies to keep a tabu list of visited local optima probably allows them to effectively cope with this type of problems, while the other algorithms cannot. Also, the greater the number of function evaluations allowed between changes, the better the performance of the *reactive-cs* respect to the *independent-cs*.

The mQSO and its variants are definitely better-suited for MPB-like problems, and specially for low dimensionality, but fail to deal with more regular, structured problems like the Ackley, Griewank or Rastrigin functions. The differences between each variant depend too much on the problem to obtain general conclusions about their global behavior.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the results obtained in this paper are in accordance with those we obtained in previous works. The outstanding performance of the cooperative strategies over other proposals was previously confirmed in a more reduced set of experiments (see [23]), as well as the overall better performance of mQSO rule-based variants over the standard mQSO (see [19]).

6. Conclusions

This work presents a study on the performance of several algorithms on different continuous Dynamic Optimization Problems (DOPs).

Eight algorithms have been chosen for the study: SORIGA, the Agents algorithm, the standard mQSO and 3 of its variations based on heuristic rules (mQSO + Change Rule, mQSO + Rand Rule, mQSO + Both), and 2 cooperative strategies based on trajectory metaheuristics, one with no cooperation between them (independent), and the other one with a cooperation scheme based on the ideas of Reactive Search.

The algorithms have been tested on the Moving Peaks Benchmark (MPB) and on dynamic versions of the well-known Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions. For each problem, a wide variety of configurations have been used, including variations of the dimensionality of the problem, the frequency of the changes on the environment, and the severity of those changes.

A recent technique, SRCS, has also been used for presenting the results of a high number of experiments when comparing several algorithms. The methodology focuses on ranking the algorithms using statistical tests, and assigning color keys to each rank, in order to create a graphical matrix. These matrices are more expressive and comprehensible than their numerical counterparts.

From the results, the following conclusions can be obtained:

- For the **MPB**: there are 3 algorithms which are better than the other 5 for some configurations. These algorithms are the *agents*, the *mqso-rand*, and the *reactive-cs*.
 - the *agents* algorithm seems to be more effective than the others for higher dimensions (15-25), and is more influenced by the severity (better with higher severity) than by the change period.
 - the *mqso-rand*, on the contrary, is better suited for lower dimensions (5-10), and is more dependent on the change period (better with higher number of function evaluations), than on the severity.
 - the *reactive-cs* seems to be better for low severity, high number of function evaluations, higher dimensionality.
- For the **Ackley** function: there are, again, 3 algorithms which are clearly better than the others: *soriga*, and the two variants of the cooperative strategies, *independent-cs* and *reactive-cs*.

- both *independent-cs* and *reactive-cs* have a very similar behaviour, clearly outperforming the rest of the algorithms for most of the configurations.
 - *soriga* is the only algorithm that performs better than the cooperative strategies for some configurations, which are mainly those with dimensionality between 10 and 20, and for very rapidly changing environments.
- For the **Griewank** and **Rastrigin** functions, the results are almost identical, with the cooperative strategies clearly dominating the rest of the algorithms, and *soriga* being the only one performing better for a reduced set of configurations, mainly very low dimensionality (5), very low change period (40-100), and for any severity. Between the cooperative strategies, *reactive-cs* seems to be slightly better than *independent-cs*.

This shows that the cooperative strategies are the best choice for problems with some kind of regular structure on their local optima distribution (e.g., Ackley, Griewank, Rastrigin). SORIGA is the best option for very rapidly changing environments. When the problem's local optima distribution is more random, like in the MPB, the mQSO + Rand Rule obtains the best results for low dimensionality, while the Agents behaves better for higher dimensionality and growing severity of the changes.

Finally, numerical results of the experiments, although not submitted for publication due to space limitations, are openly available to the scientific community. Results data files of all the experiments can be requested to the corresponding authors for future research and algorithm comparisons.

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